

Supernova studies in the SDSS-II/SNe Survey:

Spectroscopy of the peculiar SN 2007qd, and photometric properties of Type-Ia supernovae as a function of the distance to the host galaxy

Lluís Galbany i Gonzàlez

28 Octubre 2011

Outline

- Introduction
- Supernovae
- SDSS-II/SNe Survey
- The peculiar SN 2007qd
- SNe properties as a function of the distance to the host galaxy center
- Summary

Outline

- **Introduction**
- Supernovae
- SDSS-II/SNe Survey
- The peculiar SN 2007qd
- SNe properties as a function of the distance to the host galaxy center
- Summary

Discovery of the accelerated expansion

- In 1998 two teams of astronomers and physicists studying Type-Ia SNe found that the expansion rate of the universe is increasing with time: **accelerated expansion**

Supernova Cosmology Project

Perlmutter et al. 1999

High-z Supernova Team

Riess et al. 1998

- X: redshift → scale of the universe ($1+z=1/a$)
- Y: magnitude → brightness → distance → time
- History of the expansion of the universe
- **Motivation:** Understand SN properties to:
 - Control systematics
 - Reduce scatter

From Perlmutter 2003, Physics Today, 56, 53

Discovery of the accelerated expansion

- In 1998 two teams of astronomers and physicists studying Type-Ia SNe found that the expansion rate of the universe is increasing with time: **accelerated expansion**

Supernova Cosmology Project

Perlmutter et al. 1999

2011

High-z Supernova Team

Riess et al. 1998

- X: redshift \rightarrow scale of the universe ($1+z=1/a$)
- Y: magnitude \rightarrow brightness \rightarrow distance \rightarrow time
- History of the expansion of the universe
- Motivation:** Understand SN properties to:
 - Control systematics
 - Reduce scatter

From Perlmutter 2003, Physics Today, 56, 53

From magnitudes to distance to cosmology

- Knowledge about the universe comes from the analysis of the light we receive
- Magnitude: related to the integrated flux in a certain wavelength range (commonly measured using certain set of filters, Johnson-UBVRI, Sloan-ugriz)

apparent magnitude

SN flux

filter transmission

$$m_X = -2.5 \log_{10} \left[\frac{\int F(\lambda) S_X(\lambda) \lambda d\lambda}{\int F_{ref}(\lambda) S_X(\lambda) \lambda d\lambda} \right]$$

reference flux: defines the magnitude system

Basically in the visible range, ranging from UV (U) to near infrared (I)

- From m one can get the distance, from which the cosmological parameters can be measured

$$\mu(z) = m(z) - M = 25 + 5 \log_{10} d_L(z)$$

Absolute magnitude

Luminosity distance

$$d_L = \frac{c}{H_0} (1+z) \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{\Omega_M (1+z')^3 + \Omega_\Lambda}}$$

- This make sense for standard candles, which have the same M
- Type Ia supernovae are standard candles

Outline

- Introduction
- **Supernovae**
- SDSS-II/SNe Survey
- The peculiar SN 2007qd
- SNe properties as a function of the distance to the host galaxy center
- Summary

Supernovae

- Stars that have reached the end of their lives in an explosion
- Two types of explosions:
 - *Core-collapse stars*: nuclear fuel exhausted, gravity not balanced, and the star collapses.
 - *Thermonuclear explosions*: Low mass star that has evolved into a White Dwarf accretes mass from a companion until it reaches the Chandrasekhar mass ($M_{Ch} \sim 1.4 M_{SUN}$)

H and *He* transferred into WD surface, burned very fast forming *C*. After reaching M_{Ch} , *C* is turned into *O*.

Runaway detonation or deflagration that destroys the star in a few seconds

Luminosity depends primarily on ^{56}Ni mass

Details of explosion not well understood.

Since the mass is fixed (M_{Ch}), they are expected to have similar absolute magnitudes, as well having homogeneous spectra and light curves

Crab nebula (SN1054)

Observational classification

- Type Ia SNe are supposed to come from C-O WD thermonuclear explosions, which can be turned into standard candles

Spectra of Type-Ia SNe

- The spectra reveal details about their chemical composition and their evolution with time.
- The strongest features are Ca II (H 3934 & K 3968 Å) and Si II (6355 Å), blueshifted due to the velocity of the ejecta (typical velocities: $\sim 10,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$)
- **Normal features**
 - 1 week past maximum: Absorption by Intermediate Mass Elements (IME: O, Mg, Si, S, Ca), and Iron-peak elements (Fe, Co)
 - 2 weeks past maximum: the Iron-like elements dominates
- The Si II absorption is the feature that best identifies Type Ia SNe

Si II 6355 Å blueshifted (10,000 km/s) to 6150 Å and redshifted (z=0.15) to 7073 Å

$$\lambda_e = \lambda_r [1 - (v/c)] = 6355 \cdot [1 - (10^5 / 3 \cdot 10^8)]$$

$$\lambda_o = \lambda_e (1 + z) = 6150 \cdot 1.15 = 7073$$

Light-curves (LC) of Type-Ia SNe

- LC is the representation of the evolution of the SN brightness with time
- Brightness increases after the explosion up to maximum brightness (~ 15 days). Then decreases powered by the radioactive decay of ^{56}Ni (~ 30 days), and ^{56}Co (~ 70 days).
- LC are expected to have similar peak magnitudes ($M_B \sim -19.5$) and to be homogeneous. Their extreme luminosity allows the detection at large distances.
- They present a scatter of 0.3 mag at peak luminosity
- [Phillips 1993](#): Empirical Correlation: Peak brightness correlates with decline rate (Brighter SNe Ia decline more slowly).
- After correction, ~ 0.15 mag ($\sim 7\%$ distance precision)

$$\Delta m_{15} = m_B(t_{max}) - m_B(t_{max} + 15 \text{ days})$$

Photometry (I): K-correction

- At high z , the measured magnitudes correspond to different regions in the rest frame
- Plot: At $z=0.5$, U in the rest frame is mostly V but not perfectly
- These differences can be corrected adding a correction term called K-correction

$$m_Y^{Rest} = m_X^{Obs} + K_{XY}$$

Difference on the reference flux
in X and Y bands

$$K_{XY} = -2.5 \log_{10} \left[\frac{\int F_{ref}(\lambda) S_X(\lambda) \lambda d\lambda}{\int F_{ref}(\lambda) S_Y(\lambda) \lambda d\lambda} \right] + 2.5 \log_{10}(1+z) + 2.5 \log_{10} \left[\frac{\int F(\lambda) S_X(\lambda) \lambda d\lambda}{\int F[\lambda/(1+z)] S_Y(\lambda) \lambda d\lambda} \right]$$

Correction for the SN flux

- K-corrections imply knowledge of the spectrum, the SN z , and band profiles

Photometry (II): extinction

- Extinction: Presence of dust in the host galaxy that absorbs some of the emitted light, usually reemitting some in longer wavelengths, thereby leading to the dimming of the SN and reddening of its color
- Typically measured in the V band

$$m_V^{obs} = m_V^{em} + A_V$$

A_V : Absorption (increase in magnitude) in V band

- For other bands, the extinction is assumed to follow Cardelli law

$$m_X^{obs} = m_X^{em} + A_V \left(a(\lambda) + \frac{b(\lambda)}{R_V} \right)$$

$a(\lambda)$, $b(\lambda)$ known functions

R_V , determined from data, ~ 3.1 in the Milky Way

- More important at short λ , since extinction follows a $1/\lambda$ law
- Milky Way extinction well known and corrected for

Light-curve models

- Light-curve models are used to obtain distance estimations from the measured light-curves of SNe
- These models take into account all the corrections we considered (Phillips relation, K-corrections and extinction)
- The two most common are MLCS and SALT2 fitters

Light-curve models: MLC2k2

Model:

$$m_{MLCS2k2}^{t,f} = M^{t,f'} + p^{t,f'} \Delta + q^{t,f'} \Delta^2 + X_{host}^{t,f'} + X_{MW}^{t,f} + K_{ff'}^t + \mu$$

epoch band Model functions host extinction MW extinction K-corrections

Brightness-LC width parameter A_V Distance modulus

- Model functions calculated from low-z sample
- K-corrections independent from LC adjustment (measured from spectral templates)
- 3 output parameters
 - Δ related with Δm_{15} , that admits a quadratic term
 - Color variations assumed to be due to the extinction by dust of the host and follow Cardelli law (parametrized by A_V)
 - μ , the distance estimation

Light-curve models: SALT2

- Fit each light-curve using rest-frame *spectral* surfaces:

$$F(t, \lambda) = x_0 [M_0(t, \lambda) + x_1 M_1(t, \lambda)] \exp [c CL(\lambda)]$$

Mean spectral shape (blue arrow pointing to $M_0(t, \lambda)$)
 Variability (blue arrow pointing to $x_1 M_1(t, \lambda)$)
 time-independent color correction term (blue arrow pointing to $\exp [c CL(\lambda)]$)
 flux normalization (red arrow pointing to x_0)
 stretch parameter (red arrow pointing to x_1)
 color offset parameter (red arrow pointing to c)

- Distances estimated globally:

$$\mu_i = m_{B,i} - M + \alpha x_{1,i} - \beta c_i$$

$m_B = -2.5 \log [x_0 \int M_0(t, \lambda) S_B(\lambda) d\lambda]$
 M , mean absolute magnitude of a SN

α , global stretch law

β ($\sim R_V + 1$), global color law
 determined through minimizing
 the Hubble diagram scatter

- Differences from MLCS:

- not trained just on low-z data
- color variations not assumed to come only from dust

- Output parameters are $c, x_1, m_B \rightarrow \mu$

Other LC parameters

- These parameterizations reduce the scatter in the Hubble diagram to about 0.15 magnitudes
- The luminosity could also depend on other parameters, such as host galaxy morphology, star formation rate, metallicity, age...
- These dependences properly parametrized could reduce the scatter
- However, if these inhomogeneities are not accounted for by the LC parametrization, this may introduce systematic errors in the determination of the cosmology, if the mean value of the parameters depend on z
- This is one of the aims of SDSS-II Supernova Survey (SDSS-II/SNe)

Outline

- Introduction
- Supernovae
- **SDSS-II/SNe Survey**
- The peculiar SN 2007qd
- SNe properties as a function of the distance to the host galaxy center
- Summary

SN Surveys

- Situation before SDSS-II/SNe Survey
 - low z ($z < 0.1$)
 - high z ($z > 0.5$)
 - Redshift desert ($0.1 < z < 0.3$)

SN Surveys

- Situation before SDSS-II/SNe Survey
 - low z ($z < 0.1$)
 - high z ($z > 0.5$)
 - Redshift desert ($0.1 < z < 0.3$)
- SDSS-II/SNe Survey covers the redshift desert region ($0.05 < z < 0.45$)

SDSS-II/SNe Survey

Use the 2.5m SDSS telescope:

- Scan 300 deg² every 2 days in *ugriz* bands
- September 1 - November 30 of 2005-2007
- Obtain densely sampled multicolor LC

Main Goals:

- Obtain well-observed sample in the redshift desert ($z \sim 0.05-0.4$) to anchor Hubble diagram, train light-curve fitters, and explore systematics of SN Ia distances
- Probe Dark Energy in a redshift range complementary to other SN surveys
- Large survey volume: Study rare & peculiar SNe, probe outliers of population

Searching for SNe

Search

Template

Difference

g

r

i

- Image subtraction (~100,000 transients)
- Object selection (~10,000 candidates)
- Visual inspection (~2500 SNe)
- Classification (1372 SNe Ia)

SNe classes	2004	2005	2006	2007	all
[104] photo-Ia no spec-z	-	228	277	239	744
[105] photo-Ia + host spec-z	-	304	286	218	808
[106] photo-non-Ia + host spec-z	-	105	91	89	285
[111] SDSS-confirmed Ib	1	3	3	1	8
[112] SDSS-confirmed Ic	-	4	4	3	11
[113] SDSS-confirmed II	4	10	19	37	70
[115] externally-confirmed Ib	-	-	-	1	1
[117] externally-confirmed II	-	1	-	-	1
[118] externally-confirmed Ia	-	1	5	3	9
[119] likely confirmed Ia	-	16	12	9	37
[120] SDSS-confirmed Ia	16	129	197	176	518
Total	21	801	894	776	2492
Type Ia SNe					
[105]+[118]+[119]+[120] Ia	16	450	500	406	1372

SDSS SN Photometry

- Scene Modeling Photometry (SMP)
 - SN (time-varying), and host galaxy background (time-constant) modeled together
 - Constrained including images well before and well after the explosion
 - Better error determination

Spectroscopic follow-up (I)

- A fast photometric classification is needed in order to trigger the spectroscopic follow-up
- **gri** LC after 2–3 epochs are compared against a template library of LCs to estimate:
 - Type. Classification accurate (90%)
 - Redshift. Precision (5–10%)
- Spectroscopic follow-up for best candidates

Spectroscopic follow-up (II)

MDM 2.4m
APO 3.5m
KPNO 4m
Subaru 8.2m
HET 9.2m
Keck 10m
Magellan 6m
SALT 10m
TNG 3.6m
NOT 2.6m
NTT 3.6m
WHT 4.2m

ESO

- As part of the ESO team, we observed 4 nights in October-November 2007
- Received a list of candidates to observe
- Quick analysis of z and type, to trigger other spectra in higher-resolution or different λ range
- Detailed extraction (λ and flux calibrated) of SNe spectra to obtain type and redshift
 - Actually z can be obtained from
 - host features in SN spectrum (error 0.05%)
 - SN spectral features (error 0.5%)
 - host spectral redshift (for photo-Ia)

Telescope and instrument

- Telescopio Nazionale Galileo (TNG)
 - 3.58 m
 - La Palma, ORM
 - Rotational dome
- Low-Res Spectrograph (DOLORES)
 - CCD camera (2048x2048)
 - Slits (0.7", 1.0", 1.5", 2.0", 5.0")
 - Grisms wheel (LR-B, 3000-8430 Å)
 - Calibration lamps (Ne, He, Ar)

Extraction of the spectra (I)

SN 2007jh

- Field image

Extraction of the spectra (I)

SN 2007jh

- Field image
- Slit position

Extraction of the spectra (I)

SN 2007jh

- Field image
- Slit position
- Spectrum (SN, host, sky)

Extraction of the spectra (I)

SN 2007jh

- Field image
- Slit position
- Spectrum (SN, host, sky)
- Cut region and correct for bias and flat field

Extraction of the spectra (I)

SN 2007jh

- Field image
- Slit position
- Spectrum (SN, host, sky)
- Cut region and correct for bias and flat field
- Remove sky background

Extraction of the spectra (I)

SN 2007jh

- Field image
- Slit position
- Spectrum (SN, host, sky)
- Cut region and correct for bias and flat field
- Remove sky background
- Peak extraction

Extraction of the spectra (I)

SN 2007jh

- Field image
- Slit position
- Spectrum (SN, host, sky)
- Cut region and correct for bias and flat field
- Remove sky background
- Peak extraction

- Side bands and trace

Extraction of the spectra (I)

SN 2007jh

- Field image
- Slit position
- Spectrum (SN, host, sky)
- Cut region and correct for bias and flat field
- Remove sky background
- Peak extraction

- Side bands and trace
- Spectra extraction (counts/#column)

Extraction of the spectra (II): λ calibration

Arc lamps used for wavelength calibration

Extraction of the spectra (III): Flux calibration

- Measure spectrum of some standard stars
- Apply wavelength calibration
- Divide by the tabulated spectrum
- Obtain the flux calibration factor

Results

- 23 SN spectra obtained
 - 13 Type Ia
 - 7 Type II
 - 3 untyped

Outline

- Introduction
- Supernovae
- SDSS-II/SNe Survey
- **The peculiar SN 2007qd**
- SNe properties as a function of the distance to the host galaxy center
- Summary

The peculiar SN 2007qd

- One of the 23 SNe for which we obtained a spectrum, turned out to be very peculiar
- Our early notice allowed other telescopes to obtain 3 other spectra at different epochs
- Spectrum has resemblances to 2002cx and 2005hk
- The following year, 2008ha had similar spectra, and was considered a core collapse SN by *Valenti et al. 2009, Nature 459, 674*
- We will try to understand better these peculiar SNe because it is important in order to control systematics in the Hubble diagram

Photometry

- 07qd less luminous in all bands
- fast rise time (10 ± 2 days)
- Error large because there are no observations near maximum

- $m_g - m_r$ color evolution: 07qd bluer than 05hk near maximum
- dust extinction reddens, but 07qd is bluer
 - dust extinction is not the major cause of low luminosity

Light-curve analysis

MLCS and SALT2 fits: large χ^2 .
 Fitters not trained for peculiar SNe

- Simpler fit using stretch: $s=0.67$, $M_B = -15.4 \pm 0.2$
- One of the most sub-luminous SN Ia ever observed
- Comparison with normal SDSS-II/SNe at $z < 0.12$
 - 07qd and 08ha have narrower light curves and are much fainter
 - For 02cx-like, correlation between M_B and stretch remains after Phillips correction

Spectral analysis of 2007qd

Ion	τ	v_{\min}	v_{\max}	v_e	T_{exc}
C II	0.002	2.8	∞	1	10
C III	0.5	5.0	8.0	2	10
O I	9.5	2.8	6.5	3	10
O III	1.8	2.8	∞	1	10
Na I	0.5	2.8	4.5	1	10
Na I	0.3	4.5	8.0	4	10
Na I	0.1	8.0	10.0	2	10
Mg I	0.5	2.8	∞	2	12
Al I	3.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Si II	3.0	2.0	∞	1	8
Si III	2.0	2.8	∞	1	10
S II	2.7	2.8	3.3	2	10
Ca I	2.0	5.0	∞	1	10
Ca II	10.0	2.8	3.0	2	12
Ti I	1.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Cr I	2.0	2.8	4.0	2	10
Fe III	0.7	2.8	∞	1	10
Fe II	1.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Co II	3.0	2.8	∞	1	10

10^3 km s^{-1} 10^3 K

Spectral analysis of 2007qd

HET
KECK
HET

Ion	τ	v_{\min}	v_{\max}	v_e	T_{exc}
C II	0.002	2.8	∞	1	10
C III	0.5	5.0	8.0	2	10
O I	9.5	2.8	6.5	3	10
O III	1.8	2.8	∞	1	10
Na I	0.5	2.8	4.5	1	10
Na I	0.3	4.5	8.0	4	10
Na I	0.1	8.0	10.0	2	10
Mg I	0.5	2.8	∞	2	12
Al I	3.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Si II	3.0	2.0	∞	1	8
Si III	2.0	2.8	∞	1	10
S II	2.7	2.8	3.3	2	10
Ca I	2.0	5.0	∞	1	10
Ca II	10.0	2.8	3.0	2	12
Ti I	1.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Cr I	2.0	2.8	4.0	2	10
Fe III	0.7	2.8	∞	1	10
Fe II	1.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Co II	3.0	2.8	∞	1	10

10^3 km s^{-1} 10^3 K

Norm. F_λ + constant

Fe II: velocity of the ejecta
2800 km s⁻¹

Spectral analysis of 2007qd

HET
KECK
HET

Ion	τ	v_{\min}	v_{\max}	v_e	T_{exc}
C II	0.002	2.8	∞	1	10
C III	0.5	5.0	8.0	2	10
O I	9.5	2.8	6.5	3	10
O III	1.8	2.8	∞	1	10
Na I	0.5	2.8	4.5	1	10
Na I	0.3	4.5	8.0	4	10
Na I	0.1	8.0	10.0	2	10
Mg I	0.5	2.8	∞	2	12
Al I	3.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Si II	3.0	2.0	∞	1	8
Si III	2.0	2.8	∞	1	10
S II	2.7	2.8	3.3	2	10
Ca I	2.0	5.0	∞	1	10
Ca II	10.0	2.8	3.0	2	12
Ti I	1.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Cr I	2.0	2.8	4.0	2	10
Fe III	0.7	2.8	∞	1	10
Fe II	1.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Co II	3.0	2.8	∞	1	10

10^3 km s^{-1} 10^3 K

Fe II: velocity of the ejecta
2800 km s⁻¹

Spectral analysis of 2007qd

HET
KECK
HET

Ion	τ	v_{\min}	v_{\max}	v_e	T_{exc}
C II	0.002	2.8	∞	1	10
C III	0.5	5.0	8.0	2	10
O I	9.5	2.8	6.5	3	10
O III	1.8	2.8	∞	1	10
Na I	0.5	2.8	4.5	1	10
Na I	0.3	4.5	8.0	4	10
Na I	0.1	8.0	10.0	2	10
Mg I	0.5	2.8	∞	2	12
Al I	3.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Si II	3.0	2.0	∞	1	8
Si III	2.0	2.8	∞	1	10
S II	2.7	2.8	3.3	2	10
Ca I	2.0	5.0	∞	1	10
Ca II	10.0	2.8	3.0	2	12
Ti I	1.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Cr I	2.0	2.8	4.0	2	10
Fe III	0.7	2.8	∞	1	10
Fe II	1.0	2.8	∞	1	10
Co II	3.0	2.8	∞	1	10

10^3 km s^{-1} 10^3 K

Spectral comparison with 02cx-like

all spectra shifted to the rest frame

t ~ around peak

- 05hk, 07qd and 08ha are spectroscopically very similar

Spectral comparison with 02cx-like

all spectra shifted to the rest frame

t=+10 days spectra

- 05hk, 07qd and 08ha are spectroscopically very similar
- 07qd twin of 08ha
- 02cx twin of 05hk
- All of them are Ia, and constitute a single spectral class

Photospheric velocity

- There seems to be a correlation between the maximum luminosity and the photospheric velocity
- This figure confirms 07qd as a link between 08ha and other 02cx-like SNe

Discussion

- 07qd was spectroscopically similar to 02cx, 05hk and 08ha. Strong lines of Fe II and Co II are present in spectra of all four objects
- The presence of IMEs (Si II, S II) in the early-time spectra suggests the thermonuclear deflagration of C and O, and shows 07qd to be inconsistent with a core collapse event.

Contrary to *Valenti et al. 2009, Nature, 459, 674*
which states that all 02cx-like were core collapse SNe

- Correlations exist between 02cx-like peak luminosity, photospheric velocity, and light-curve stretch, and the events span a sequence from 02cx to 08ha.

02cx-like are
Type Ia SNe

+

link between
08ha and 02cx-like

Outline

- Introduction
- Supernovae
- SDSS-II/SNe Survey
- The peculiar SN 2007qd
- **SNe properties as a function of the distance to the host galaxy center**
- Summary

Motivation

- Accounting for other dependences on SN luminosity, can reduce the scatter in Hubble diagram and reduce the systematic errors.
- There have been several studies of SNe properties depending on **global** characteristics of the hosts
- Look for dependencies between SN Ia properties and its projected distance to the host galaxy center, using the distance as a proxy for **local** galaxy properties (local star-formation rate, local metallicity, etc.).
- Use SDSS-II/SNe Survey 3-year sample
- Fit LCs using both **MLCS2k2** and **SALT2**. Determine:
 - Color (A_V, c)
 - Decline rate (Δ, x_1)
 - Residuals in the fit to the Hubble diagram ($\delta\mu$).
- Correlate these parameters with several definitions of the distance of the SN to the center of the host galaxy

Sample

- The SDSS-II SN sample consists of **1318** SNe Ia in the range $0 < z < 0.45$
- **559** SNe Ia confirmed spectroscopically (*Spec-Ia* sample)
- **759** SNe photometrically classified as Type Ia from their LCs (*Photo-Ia* sample)
- We restrict the sample to redshifts $z < 0.25$ where the completeness is still relatively high
- The closest galaxy within an angular separation of $20''$ was matched using the SDSS DR7

17 no host

	Spec-Ia	Photo-Ia	Total
SN Ia sample ($z < 0.45$)	559	759	1318
Redshift < 0.25	376	232	608
Identified host galaxy	363	228	591

Light-curve fitters

- LC fitted through **MLCS2k2** and **SALT2**. Parameters obtained:

- LC shape (Δ and x_1)

$$M = -19.41 \pm 0.04$$

- SN color (A_V and c)

$$\alpha = 0.131 \pm 0.052$$

$$\beta = 3.26 \pm 0.49$$

$$\Lambda\text{CDM: } \Omega_M = 0.274 = 1 - \Omega_\Lambda$$

From full SDSS-II/SNe sample

- Hubble residual (μ_{MLCS} and $\mu_{SALT2} = m_B - M + \alpha x_1 - \beta c$) $\rightarrow \delta\mu = \mu_{LC} - \mu_{TH}$

- We apply LC quality cuts (*MLCS, SALT2*)

- 5 obs between $t_{\max} - 20 < t_{\text{obs}} < t_{\max} + 70$ (60) days
- 1 obs $t_{\text{obs}} < t_{\max} - 2$ (0) days
- 1 obs $t_{\text{obs}} > t_{\max} + 10$ (9.5) days
- 1 obs with $S/N > 5$ in *gri*
- Probability of LC fit > 0.001

- And Parameter cuts

- $\Delta > -0.4$
- $-4.5 < x_1 < 2.0$
- $-0.3 < c < 0.6$

	Spec-Ia		Photo-Ia		Total	
	MLCS	SALT2	MLCS	SALT2	MLCS	SALT2
SN Ia sample ($z < 0.45$)	559		759		1318	
Redshift < 0.25	376		232		608	
Identified host galaxy	363		228		591	
LC quality cuts	228	217	115	125	343	342
LC parameter cuts	203	209	110	111	313	320

Galactocentric distances (GCD)

- Measurement of the angular separation (θ) between the host galaxy center and the SN, and physical (projected) distance using z

$$PGCD = d_A \times \theta$$

$$d_A = \frac{c}{H_0} \frac{1}{(1+z_{host})} \int_0^{z_{host}} \frac{dz'}{\sqrt{\Omega_M(1+z')^3 + \Omega_\Lambda}}$$

$$H_0 = 70.4 \pm 1.4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$$

- Due to different sizes of the **host galaxies** we use 3 distance normalization methods to allow comparisons

- **Petrosian radius 50 (P50)**: radius of a circle that contains 50% of the galaxy flux

- **Sérsic profile (SER)**: distance to the center of the ellipse containing half the luminosity

- de Vaucouleurs (DEV) profile ($n=4$, for **ellipticals**)

- exponential (EXP) profile ($n=1$, for **spirals**)

$$I(r) = I_0 \exp \left[-a_n (r/r_e)^{1/n} \right]$$

- **Isophotal ellipse (ISO)**: distance to the center of the ellipse containing 25 mag/arcsec²

- We then apply cuts on distance measurements:

- $\sigma(\theta) < 0.5''$

- $\sigma(PGCD) < 1 \text{ kpc}$

- $\sigma(R) < 0.5''$

- $\sigma(R)/R < 1$

- $NGCD \equiv \theta/R < 10$

	Spec-Ia		Photo-Ia		Total	
	MLCS	SALT2	MLCS	SALT2	MLCS	SALT2
SN Ia sample ($z < 0.45$)	559		759		1318	
Redshift < 0.25	376		232		608	
Identified host galaxy	363		228		591	
LC quality cuts	228	217	115	125	343	342
LC parameter cuts	203	209	110	111	313	320
Distance cuts	171	177	95	94	266	271

Host typing

- 2 criteria used in order to separate the hosts in elliptical and spiral
- Inverse concentration index (P50/P90)
- Best brightness profile fit (DEV/EXP)
- Selection made on agreement on both criteria

	Spec-Ia		Photo-Ia		Total	
	MLCS	SALT2	MLCS	SALT2	MLCS	SALT2
SN Ia sample ($z < 0.45$)	559		759		1318	
Redshift < 0.25	376		232		608	
Identified host galaxy	363		228		591	
LC quality cuts	228	217	115	125	343	342
LC parameter cuts	203	209	110	111	313	320
Distance cuts	171	177	95	94	266	271
Consistent host type	128	132	64	65	192	197

MLCS: 127 spirals
65 ellipticals

SALT2: 131 spirals
66 ellipticals

GCD distributions

Analysis procedure

- We correlate A_V , Δ , c , x_1 and Hubble residuals with the PGCD and the 3 normalized distances
- For every combination of LC parameter and distance measurement, SNe are binned in distance (at least 5 SNe per bin, or joined), for all the SNe, and separating host types
 - Measurement of the mean value in each bin, for both LC parameter and distance
 - Linear fit of all the SNe, and separating host types
 - Compute reduced χ^2 and significance of the slope are calculated
 - We focus on results with slope different from 0 with more than 2σ significance and reduced $\chi^2 < 2$
- We also split the sample in 2 bins (Near-Far) with same #SNe in each bin
 - Measurement of the mean and the scatter, and calculate the significance in the difference between the 2 bins
 - We focus on results with a difference with more than 2σ significance

bin width	
PGCD	0.5 kpc
P50	0,25
SER	0,25
ISO	0,05

Results: color (A_V and c)

- We find 2 (related) trends with very high significance and good fit quality:
 - A_V and c decrease with physical GCD with significant slopes (4.9 and 4.4σ), and good reduced χ^2/dof (0.6 and 0.9), when consider the whole sample

Results: color (A_V and c)

- Linear fit: A_V and c decreases with distance. Most extinguished explosions occur close to the center of the host galaxies

A_V

c

Distance unit	Host type	Slope	Sig. ^a	χ^2/dof	dof	Distance unit	Host type	Slope	Sig. ^a	χ^2/dof	dof
kpc	All	-0.0082 ± 0.0017	-4.9	0.6	17	kpc	All	-0.0032 ± 0.0007	-4.4	0.9	18
P50	All	-0.039 ± 0.016	-2.5	0.6	9	P50	All	-0.011 ± 0.008	-1.5	0.9	9
P50	Spiral	-0.046 ± 0.023	-2.0	1.1	8	P50	Spiral	-0.019 ± 0.011	-1.8	1.1	8

- 2-bin mean: low significances with P50 and EXP. Near SNe most extinguished

A_V

Distance unit	Host type	Near \bar{n}	Far \bar{f}	Difference $\bar{f} - \bar{n}$	Sig. ^a	c
P50	<u>Spiral</u>	0.420 ± 0.038	0.305 ± 0.027	-0.115 ± 0.047	-2.5	-1.2
<u>exp</u>	<u>Spiral</u>	0.410 ± 0.037	0.315 ± 0.029	-0.095 ± 0.047	-2.0	-1.5

- 2-bin scatter

A_V

Distance unit	Host type	Near σ_n	Far σ_f	Difference $\sigma_f - \sigma_n$	Sig. ^a	c
kpc	All	0.305 ± 0.036	0.223 ± 0.019	-0.082 ± 0.040	-2.0	-0.5
ISO	All	0.307 ± 0.035	0.217 ± 0.019	-0.090 ± 0.040	-2.3	-0.9

Results: Decline rate (Δ and x_1)

- Linear fit: we find weak correlation in ellipticals, larger Δ (dimmer SNe) are found at large GCD

Δ

Distance unit	Host type	Slope	Sig. ^a	χ^2/dof	dof	Spiral Sig.
kpc	Elliptical	0.0220 ± 0.0092	2.4	2.1	7	-1.6
P50	Elliptical	0.092 ± 0.050	1.9	0.7	5	-1.2
ISO	Elliptical	0.81 ± 0.45	1.8	1.1	3	-0.4
deV	Elliptical	0.103 ± 0.043	2.4	1.4	5	-0.5

- Also seen in 2-bin, but with less significance

Δ

Distance unit	Host type	2- bin Sig.
kpc	Elliptical	1.9
P50	Elliptical	1.8
ISO	Elliptical	1.7
deV	Elliptical	1.3

- no correlations found in x_1

Results: Hubble residuals ($\delta\mu$)

- Linear fit: we only find a weak correlation between $\delta\mu_{\text{SALT2}}$ and EXP normalization. $\delta\mu_{\text{SALT2}}$ in spirals increases with distance

$\delta\mu_{\text{SALT2}}$

Distance unit	Host type	Slope	Sig. ^a	χ^2/dof	dof
exp	Spiral	0.030 ± 0.014	2.2	1.1	10

- nothing in 2-bin measuring mean
- 2-bin scatter: larger scatter close to the center of the galaxy, specially in spirals, but also considering the whole sample

$\delta\mu_{\text{MLCS}}$

$\delta\mu_{\text{SALT2}}$

Distance unit	Host type	$\delta\mu_{\text{MLCS}}$				$\delta\mu_{\text{SALT2}}$			
		Near σ_n	Far σ_f	Difference $\sigma_f - \sigma_n$	Sig. ^a	Near σ_n	Far σ_f	Difference $\sigma_f - \sigma_n$	Sig. ^a
kpc	All	0.265 ± 0.030	0.217 ± 0.021	-0.048 ± 0.036	-1.3	0.231 ± 0.025	0.184 ± 0.014	-0.046 ± 0.029	-1.6
	Elliptical	0.233 ± 0.029	0.187 ± 0.030	-0.046 ± 0.042	-1.1	0.162 ± 0.022	0.209 ± 0.027	0.047 ± 0.035	1.4
	Spiral	0.277 ± 0.036	0.201 ± 0.025	-0.076 ± 0.044	-1.7	0.256 ± 0.032	0.163 ± 0.014	-0.093 ± 0.035	-2.7
P50	All	0.284 ± 0.029	0.193 ± 0.016	-0.091 ± 0.033	-2.7	0.240 ± 0.025	0.173 ± 0.014	-0.067 ± 0.028	-2.4
	Elliptical	0.234 ± 0.029	0.187 ± 0.030	-0.047 ± 0.042	-1.1	0.175 ± 0.022	0.200 ± 0.028	0.024 ± 0.035	0.7
	Spiral	0.293 ± 0.035	0.174 ± 0.014	-0.119 ± 0.038	-3.1	0.261 ± 0.031	0.154 ± 0.013	-0.108 ± 0.034	-3.2
ISO	All	0.286 ± 0.030	0.188 ± 0.016	-0.098 ± 0.034	-2.9	0.241 ± 0.025	0.172 ± 0.014	-0.068 ± 0.029	-2.4
	Elliptical	0.228 ± 0.030	0.193 ± 0.030	-0.035 ± 0.042	-0.8	0.166 ± 0.023	0.208 ± 0.027	0.042 ± 0.035	1.2
	Spiral	0.291 ± 0.037	0.181 ± 0.016	-0.110 ± 0.040	-2.7	0.266 ± 0.031	0.147 ± 0.012	-0.119 ± 0.034	-3.6
deV	Elliptical	0.218 ± 0.027	0.205 ± 0.033	-0.013 ± 0.042	-0.3	0.165 ± 0.023	0.208 ± 0.027	0.043 ± 0.035	1.2
exp	Spiral	0.274 ± 0.037	0.206 ± 0.024	-0.069 ± 0.044	-1.5	0.238 ± 0.028	0.188 ± 0.030	-0.050 ± 0.041	-1.2

Discussion

- We find some indications that SNe in elliptical galaxies tend to have narrower LC (larger Δ , fainter SNe) if they explode farther from the galaxy core
 - This could be explained by the difficulty to detect faint SNe close to the galaxy center, where the galaxy light is stronger (selection effect)
- We find strong indications of a decrease in color with distance
 - If most of the variability in color is due to dust, and dust is expected to decrease with distance from the center, this would be expected
 - Due to the difficulty to observe faint SNe close to the galaxy center, we would expect fewer dust extinguished SNe (with high A_V) at small distances. However, this is opposite of what we find, so maybe the selection effect is not too large
- We do not find any correlation between the Hubble residuals and the GCD
 - Since GCD can be used as a proxy for the local metallicity, this can be seen as an indication of a limited correlation between Hubble residuals and local metallicity.
 - This does not confirm a recent result (D'Andrea et al. 1110.5517, ApJ accepted), which finds a correlation between Hubble residuals and global metallicity

Outline

- Introduction
- Supernovae
- SDSS-II/SNe Survey
- The peculiar SN 2007qd
- SNe properties as a function of the distance to the host galaxy center
- **Summary**

Summary

- This thesis is an end to end work about Type Ia SNe:
From the spectra measurement and reduction to two different analyses encompassing spectroscopy and photometry of Type Ia SNe
- Spectroscopic analysis of the peculiar type Ia SN 07qd, a link between an extremely faint SN (08ha) and a subgroup of low-brightness SNe (02cx-like)
This analysis indicated the thermonuclear explosion of 07qd, contradicting a previous analysis stating that all 02cx-like were core collapse events
- Study of correlations between SN photometric parameters and the SN distance to the center to the host galaxy.
Strong indications of a decrease in extinction with distance (expected)
Hint of an increment of Δ (narrower LC, dimmer SN) with distance, in elliptical hosts (could be due to selection effects)
We have not found any unexpected correlations between light-curves and distances
Therefore, this analysis limits the systematic errors that could be due to these dependencies